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Future

D6.1 – THE NOUS ARCHITECTURE AND OPEN-SOURCE DEVELOPMENT PLATFORM (1ST VERSION)

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D6.1: THE NOUS ARCHITECTURE AND OPEN-SOURCE DEVELOPMENT PLATFORM

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable presents the NOUS Reference Architecture and Open-Source Development Platform, defining a federated, open, and policy-driven framework that integrates compute, edge, and data resources to enable secure data sharing, distributed computation, and edge intelligence across domains. Aligned with the European Interoperability Reference Architecture (EIRA) and the European Interoperability Framework (EIF), the architecture adopts a layered and modular approach supporting IaaS, PaaS, and MLaaS services while ensuring interoperability, data sovereignty, and regulatory compliance. Central to the design are the Data Space Participant (DSP) and Data Space Infrastructure Participant (DSIP), complemented by the NOUS Data Agent (NDA), the NOUS Infrastructure Agent (NIA), and Data Space Common Services providing identity, authorization, governance, and service discovery. The deliverable also describes the supporting open-source development platform, DevSecOps mechanisms, and example instantiations, offering a comprehensive technical reference and foundation for the implementation, testing, and validation of the NOUS ecosystem.</p>
Keywords	Data Spaces, Federated Infrastructure, Data Sovereignty, Cloud-Edge Continuum, Policy-Aware Resource Discovery, Federated Learning

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The NOUS project aims to design and implement a federated, open, and policy-driven architecture that enables secure data sharing, distributed computation, and edge intelligence across multiple domains and stakeholders. In line with European Data Space principles, NOUS seeks to lower the barriers for trusted data and compute collaboration while ensuring data sovereignty, interoperability, and compliance with regulatory and governance requirements.

This deliverable presents the NOUS Reference Architecture and Open-Source Development Platform, capturing the results of the architectural design activities carried out within the project. The document describes the key architectural layers, building blocks, and interactions that collectively enable the NOUS ecosystem, including data management, infrastructure provisioning, application orchestration, and user-facing services.

The core of the NOUS architecture is structured around the Data Space Participant (DSP) and the Data Space Infrastructure Participant (DSIP), which together enable the seamless integration of data, compute, and edge resources. The NOUS Data Agent (NDA) supports secure data exchange, data orchestration, and application management, while the NOUS Infrastructure Agent (NIA) provides infrastructure discovery, provisioning, orchestration, and networking capabilities. These components are complemented by Data Space Common Services, which ensure identity management, authorization, governance, interoperability, and service discovery across the ecosystem.

In addition to the architectural description, this deliverable outlines the open-source development platform supporting NOUS, detailing how architectural components are instantiated, integrated, and deployed. The document also presents example instantiations of the reference architecture, demonstrating how NOUS can be applied in practical scenarios involving distributed data processing, AI workload execution, and cross-domain collaboration. Overall, this deliverable provides a comprehensive and coherent view of the NOUS architecture, serving as a technical reference for project partners, developers, and stakeholders, and laying the foundation for future implementation, validation, and exploitation activities.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Certification Authority
CLI	Command Line Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DoA	Description of Action
DS	Data Space
DSCS	Data Space Common Services
DSP	Data Space Participant
DSIP	Data Space Infrastructure Participant
DT	Digital Twin
E2E	End-to-End
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connector
FL	Federated Learning
FOSS	Free and Open-Source Software
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High Performance Computing
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MLaaS	Machine Learning as a Service
NDA	NOUS Data Agent
NIA	NOUS Infrastructure Agent
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure

PoC	Proof of Concept
RA	Reference Architecture
REST	Representational State Transfer
SLA	Service Level Agreement
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UI	User Interface
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 SCOPE AND OBJECTIVE OF THIS DELIVERABLE

The scope of this deliverable is to define and document the NOUS Reference Architecture and the associated open-source development platform. It consolidates the architectural concepts, design decisions, and technical building blocks developed within the project, providing a unified and consistent architectural view of the NOUS ecosystem. The main objectives of this deliverable are to:

- Describe the overall NOUS reference architecture and its layered structure
- Define the roles and responsibilities of the main architectural entities, including the DSP, DSIP, NDA, and NIA
- Detail the core building blocks supporting data exchange, infrastructure provisioning, application orchestration, and governance
- Illustrate how data, compute, and edge resources are integrated and managed in a federated and policy-aware manner
- Provide example instantiations of the architecture to demonstrate its applicability in real-world scenarios.

This deliverable serves as a technical reference for subsequent implementation, integration, and validation activities within the NOUS project.

1.2 DELIVERABLE STRUCTURE

The remainder of this deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the background concepts, architectural principles, and design drivers that inform the NOUS reference architecture.
- Section 3 presents the NOUS Reference Architecture and Building Blocks, describing the main architectural layers and their interactions.
- Section 4 provides a detailed description of the core components of the NOUS Data Agent and NOUS Infrastructure Agent.
- Section 5 presents example instantiations of the NOUS reference architecture, illustrating its application in representative scenarios.
- Section 6 describes the open-source development platform supporting the NOUS architecture, including integration and deployment aspects.
- Section 7 concludes the deliverable and outlines future work.

2 NOUS AS THE ENABLER OF #DATA #COMPUTE #EDGE

Europe is facing a rapid expansion in the volume of data generated across sectors, creating a strong demand for reliable, competitive, and accessible storage but also for processing capabilities. The NOUS envisions to promote the European data service ecosystem across public and private sector, providing the blueprint for data-sharing models, computation closer to end users through edge technologies, and high performance and scalable on demand computational capabilities through HPC and quantum computers. The vision behind the NOUS follows the design principles of the Simpl Open¹, the open-source middleware core of EU to make data sharing and interoperability easier across European Data Spaces and cloud-to-edge environments. NOUS, like the Simpl Open is designed as a vendor-neutral middleware to build and connect secure, interoperable data ecosystems, enabling data and services to be exchanged safely across sectors and borders. It supports trusted and secure data exchange and interoperability across EU Data Spaces, and it will help users, data providers, and application/infrastructure providers work together in a decentralized network.

The NOUS middleware functions as an abstract component that each actor must deploy to join and participate in the ecosystem. Beyond simply enabling the creation of individual Data Spaces, the middleware provides the interoperability layer that connects different Data Spaces, users, application providers, and infrastructure participants, allowing them to interact seamlessly. Its architecture is designed to support large numbers of participants interacting simultaneously, ensuring scalability and robust collaboration across the ecosystem.

2.1 NOUS ACTORS IN A FEDERATED ENVIRONMENT

The NOUS ecosystem adopts a user centric approach that revolves around the participating actors of the platform and their specific and interchangeable roles. These actors represent a distributed network of organizations collaborating within an open ecosystem. As it is depicted in Figure 1, a connective layer is implemented across all actors allowing them to exchange but also to get access to assets. The actors that have been identified are the following:

Governance Authority: The entity responsible for defining and enforcing the rules, policies, standards, and trust framework of the Data Space. It ensures compliance, sets participation conditions, and manages certification or quality requirements.

Data Participant: An organization or entity that provides, consumes, or exchanges data within the ecosystem. They contribute datasets, metadata, or services and may also use data supplied by others.

Infrastructure Participant: A provider of the foundational computing, storage, networking, or cloud-to-edge resources required for the ecosystem to operate.

Application Provider: A party that develops and operates software services or applications running on top of the Data Space. They leverage available data and infrastructure to deliver value-added functionality to end users.

End User: The individual or organization that directly interacts with applications or services built on top of the Data Space. They benefit from the shared assets but do not manage infrastructure or provide data themselves.

The NOUS smart middleware, represented by the NOUS Agent, spans across these actors, enabling data and asset sharing between them. It offers a set of shared core services that any Data Space can rely on and as it is neutral with respect to sector-specific rules or requirements, each Data Space

¹ <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu>

can add its own complementary services on top of the core layer. These additional services might include common data models and standardization engines, certification schemes, mechanisms for evaluating data quality and data lifecycle management or access to specific infrastructure. In this way, a Data Space turns from a basic asset-exchange environment into a structured ecosystem where assets gain real value for its members.

FIGURE 1. THE ACTORS OF THE NOUS ECOSYSTEM

These roles can be seen as different “flavors” of the same underlying Data Space infrastructure, each representing a distinct way of engaging with the shared technical backbone. All actors rely on the same core middleware and interoperability services provided through the NOUS Agent. However, they interact with it from different perspectives, whether contributing data, running applications, providing compute resources, consuming services, or enforcing rules. As they all operate atop the same foundation, these roles can easily overlap or evolve over time, allowing participants to fully benefit by the modularity and scalability of the NOUS ecosystem to adopt and adapt the “flavor” that best matches their capabilities while remaining fully integrated within the unified Data Space environment.

2.2 NOUS INTER AND CROSS SECTORAL INTERACTIONS

As it can be seen on Figure 2, within a Data Space ecosystem, the five actor types interact in a fluid, collaborative environment where roles can shift depending on context and needs. A single entity may simultaneously provide datasets as a Data Participant, run domain-specific services as an Application Provider, and consume insights as an End User. Similarly, an entity offering computational or storage resources as an Infrastructure Participant may also operate applications that rely on its own infrastructure. The Governance Authority oversees the shared rules and trust framework, but even governance responsibilities can be distributed, with certain tasks delegated to participants or applications that enforce policies automatically. This dynamic model allows actors to take on multiple responsibilities, enabling flexible cooperation, efficient resource use, and the emergence of new value chains as participants move between roles while operating within the same interoperable ecosystem.

FIGURE 2. EXAMPLE OF HOW A SET OF DISTRIBUTED ACTORS MIGHT INTERCONNECT TO FORM A DATA SPACE.

Beyond the support of the creation of individual Data Spaces, the NOUS platform also enables them to interoperate (Figure 3). When multiple Data Spaces adopt the same middleware, they become more easily connected, allowing certain services to operate across Data Space boundaries. To illustrate this concept, the accompanying diagram shows one possible configuration of distributed actors forming a Data Space. This is just a single example—many different interaction models are possible. The number of participants represented by each actor type or involved in a Data Space depends only on what is technically feasible, meaning the ecosystem can scale to large numbers of stakeholders.

FIGURE 3. INTEROPERABLE DATA SPACES THROUGH THE NOUS AGENT

3 NOUS REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE & BUILDING BLOCKS

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. presents the NOUS reference architecture, a multi-vendor, large-scale, modular, and interoperable architecture which integrates Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS), and Machine Learning-as-a-Service (MLaaS) elements. This architecture illustrates how data, applications, and infrastructure resources are federated across distributed locations, enabling secure, resilient, and cloud-to-edge operations. It facilitates the publishing, discovery, and exchange of both data and infrastructure resources among heterogeneous, mutually untrusted parties, while ensuring transparency and enabling trust through verifiable mechanisms. By facilitating secure and federated collaboration, the NOUS architecture empowers stakeholders to collect and share data to support data-driven decisions using advanced computational resources.

For the design of the reference architecture presented in ¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia., several inputs and design decisions were taken into consideration, including:

- The functional and technical requirements elicitation for the NOUS architecture and its components, as defined in Deliverable D2.1 – “Status quo, gap analysis, requirements, and project evaluation framework”.
- The Simpl-Open framework², which provides an open source, secure middleware supporting data access and interoperability across European data initiatives and distributed environments.
- The need to encapsulate the complete set of components and functionalities defined in the Description of Action (DoA). Rather than representing a single, unified system instance, the NOUS Reference Architecture provides a comprehensive and federated architectural view that integrates all required building blocks to support an environment across multiple domains, use cases, and deployment scenarios.

FIGURE 4: NOUS REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/simpl>

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. reference architecture diagram is consisted of the following layers:

- Data Space Participant (DSP) which represents a group of components and systems for managing and sharing data applied to a Data Space actor.
- Data Space Infrastructure Participant (DSIP) which represents a group of components and systems for managing and provisioning infrastructure resources applied to a Data Space actor.
- Data Space Common Services (DSCS) provides essential services, functionalities, and methodologies that are shared across the Data Space environment.
- User Dashboards & Services, which provides various dashboards and domain-specific services for end-users to interact with the Data Space environment.

The proposed architecture view covers all the key aspects of NOUS (i.e., data, compute, and edge), and the components are color-coded to indicate their functional role. These colored areas highlight how each component relates to the main functional domains of NOUS:

- #compute (orange)
- #edge (purple)
- #data (blue)
- Core & Optional services (yellow, gray)
- Runtime environment (white)

3.1 DATA SPACE PARTICIPANT (DSP)

The DSP represents a group of components and systems applied to a Data Space actor. It can be hosted locally, in the cloud, or at the edge, enabling the collection, processing, and sharing of data among heterogeneous and potentially untrusted actors within the Data Space environment. By integrating the DSP into the architecture, participants can seamlessly collaborate, share, and consume data and make informed, data-driven decisions based on the exchanged and processed information.

3.1.1 NOUS DATA AGENT (NDA)

The NOUS Data Agent (NDA) facilitates the exchange and processing of data within NOUS ecosystem. It consists of various sub-components and functionalities that enable seamless data management and collaboration within the Data Space context. The components included in the NDA are described in detail below.

3.1.1.1 DATA EXCHANGE

The Data Exchange group of components enables the secure, sovereign, and efficient exchange of data among Data Space participants. It facilitates data discovery, policy negotiation, contract management, transfer, and ingestion while strictly adhering to established governance rules, sovereign sharing policies and agreements.

- **Control Plane.** The Control Plane is responsible for managing assets, policies, contracts, and governance mechanisms that regulate data sharing, discovery, and exchange within the NOUS Data Space. It ensures that all interactions among participants comply with defined rules, sovereign framework, enabling a secure, transparent, and governed data exchange environment.

- **Local Assets Catalog.** The Local Assets Catalog enables providers to register information related to their own sharing assets, which is required for supporting the publishing, contract negotiation and transfer process.
- **Contract Manager.** The Contract Manager manages data sharing agreements and contracts, ensuring compliance with defined policies, permissions, and privacy requirements for the exchange process.
- **Policy Negotiation.** The Policy Negotiation component facilitates the negotiation and agreement on data usage policies and restrictions between providers and consumers. It supports the establishment of transparent and verifiable agreements, ensuring that data and resource sharing occur under accepted governance conditions
- **Data Plane Orchestration.** The Data Plane Orchestration component orchestrates the execution and synchronization of data plane processes, including data transfer, actuation, control, and ingestion. It optimizes data flow and processing within the Data Space.
- **Data Plane.** The Data Plane is responsible for executing the actual data transfer, actuation, control, and data ingestion and provides functionalities to access various types of data resources and transfer them between participants. It implements the following components:
 - **Data Transfer.** The Data Transfer component facilitates secure and sovereign data exchange among different Data Space participants. It handles the transfer of diverse data types – including operational, analytical, and AI-related data.
 - **Actuation & Control.** Allows Data Space participants to control physical elements, such as machines and sensors, in response to circular economy data insights. It enables the implementation of circular economy strategies, such as optimizing resource usage and reducing waste.
 - **Data Ingestion Adapter.** The Data Ingestion Adapter manages the collection and integration of data from heterogeneous resources, including IoT infrastructures, and virtualized services into the NOUS ecosystem. It ensures seamless data acquisition, transformation, and synchronization, enabling comprehensive processing, analytics, AI workflows and data sharing.
- **DID Registry.** The DID (Decentralized Identifier) Registry component operates in a decentralized manner, providing a unique identification mechanism for participants, data sources, and entities within the Data Space. It ensures the integrity and authenticity of digital identities associated with different actors.
- **Federated Catalog.** The Federated Catalog component enables decentralized, scalable, and policy-compliant discovery of data assets, allowing Data Space participants to explore and identify offerings published by other participants.
- **Data Persistence.** The Data Persistence component is responsible for the storage and management of both “Raw Local Data” and “Formatted Data”, ensuring the availability of historical data for analysis, auditing, and decision-making purposes. It handles data in various structured and unstructured forms, such as time series data, relational datasets, analytical records, and Digital Twin (DT) representations, providing a unified approach to data preservation.

3.1.1.2 APPLICATION AND DATA ORCHESTRATION

The Application and Data Orchestration group of components within the NDA includes several sub-components and functionalities that support seamless integration and management of applications and data. This group encompasses components such as Application Services, External Applications & Services, Load Balancing, Edge Interoperability Mediator, Workflow Configuration, Data Routing

and Data Bus. These components enable the execution of various tasks such as data pre-processing, data analytics, interoperability operations, model training, and access to third-party cloud-based platforms. Specifically, the Application & Data Orchestration is consisted of the following components:

- **Data Bus.** Facilitates the exchange of data among different components and services within the NDA. It provides a centralized communication channel for data sharing and collaboration, enabling real-time data updates and synchronization.
- **Workflow Configuration.** Configures and manages workflows for processing and analyzing data. It enables the creation of automated data processing pipelines related to the NOUS use cases.
- **Data Routing.** Routes data to appropriate destinations within the NDA ensuring seamless data flow and interoperability. It directs data to specific applications, analytics modules, or storage systems for further processing or analysis.
- **External Applications & Services.** Integrates third-party platforms, cloud-based tools, and external data providers into the NOUS ecosystem, thereby enabling participants to enhance their analytical capabilities through access to external APIs, and domain-specific industrial or research platforms.
- **Load Balancing.** Implements mechanisms for intelligent distribution of data and computation workloads across edge, fog, and cloud environments. It employs algorithms to dynamically allocate processing tasks based on network conditions, workloads and latency constrains.
- **Application Services.** Encompasses various applications that can be utilized within the NOUS ecosystem, including data pre-processing and standardization, parallel computation, federating learning and inference, and data analytics services.
 - **Application Management.** Manages various applications and workflows, including parallel processing, data pre-processing and standardization, federated learning, and synchronization tasks, ensuring efficient resource management and coordinated execution.
 - **Parallel Processing.** Enables the efficient execution of computationally intensive tasks across distributed cloud/edge infrastructures. It leverages optimized parallel execution patterns and non-blocking mechanisms to enhance efficiency in data analytics and AI workloads.
 - **Federated Learning:** Supports decentralized and privacy-preserving model training across distributed participants without sharing raw data. It preserves data sovereignty while aggregating locally trained models into a global model, enabling collaborative intelligence across the NOUS ecosystem.
 - **Data Standardization.** Ensures the harmonization and interoperability of heterogeneous datasets. It aligns data formats and semantics with shared standards and vocabularies, enabling consistent data exchange and analytics across heterogeneous entities.
 - **Event/DS Sync.** Implements synchronization and data publication mechanisms that connects the event-based environments with the Data Space components. It ensures that all event-based data assets are registered in the Control Plane, where their metadata is published and made discoverable within the Data Space environment.

3.2 DATA SPACE INFRASTRUCTURE PARTICIPANT (DSIP)

The Data Space Infrastructure Participant (DSIP) represents a group of components and physical resources applied to a Data Space actor. It focuses on the virtualization, management, provisioning,

and orchestration of infrastructure- and platform-level offerings. The DSIP enables participants to discover, allocate, and utilize computational and storage resources across heterogeneous and potentially untrusted actors within the Data Space environment. By integrating the DSIP into the overall architecture, participants can seamlessly gain access to scalable infrastructure capabilities that support high-performance computing (e.g., HPC network and Quantum Computers), AI model training and deployment, and distributed data storing and processing, while ensuring compliance with established policies and regulatory requirements.

3.2.1 NOUS INFRASTRUCTURE AGENT (NIA)

The NOUS Infrastructure Agent (NIA) manages, orchestrates, and provisions infrastructure-level and platform-level services within the NOUS ecosystem. It consists of multiple sub-components that provide the interface between the Data Space layer and the underlying physical infrastructure. All offerings deployed through the NIA are discoverable and accessible using a service catalogue. In this context, discoverable refers to services that are visible and accessible to authorized participants within the Data Space environment. These components include:

3.2.1.1 MACHINE LEARNING AS A SERVICE (MLAAS)

The MLaaS component provides a complete environment for AI model training, deployment, and lifecycle management. It enables participants to train, evaluate, deploy, and monitor AI models securely and efficiently across federated infrastructures.

- **AI Provisioning.** The AI Provisioning enables users to discover, allocate, and configure the computational resources required for AI training and inference. It supports both physical and virtual resources – such as CPUs, GPUs, and accelerators – based on the model complexity, allowing users to focus on model experimentation, tuning, and deployment.
- **Analytics Provisioning.** The Analytics Provisioning provides users with access to high-level data analytics services required for data exploration and large-scale analytics computations, without requiring the deployment or management of local analytic frameworks.

3.2.1.2 PLATFORM AS A SERVICE (PAAS)

The PaaS component provides a comprehensive environment that enables the development, deployment, and orchestration of data-driven applications and services within the Data Space environment. It offers a unified operational layer that abstracts the complexity of the underlying infrastructure while promoting interoperability and trust among participants. Within this component, Blockchain and Database services are integrated as core services that extend the PaaS capabilities and ensure efficient, secure, and reliable data operations.

- **Blockchain.** The Blockchain enables users to access resources requiring for decentralized trust, immutability, and transparency. It functions as a trust-enabling middleware service, supporting audit logging, traceability, proof-of-origin.
- **Database.** The Database provides users with managed data storage and retrieval capabilities, supporting relations, non-relational, time series and graph database systems. It ensures secure, scalable, and high-performance data management for analytical and transactional workloads.

3.2.1.3 INFRASTRUCTURE AS A SERVICE (IAAS)

The IaaS component provides virtualized computing and storage capabilities required for all higher-level services. It ensures the elastic scalability and reliability of the underlying infrastructure, enabling efficient resource utilization across Cloud, Edge, and HPC environments.

- **High-Performance Computing (HPC).** The HPC provides access to large-scale, high-throughput computing clusters that support data-intensive simulations, training of complex AI models, and large-scale processing tasks.
- **Quantum.** The Quantum component adds computing capabilities, enabling hybrid quantum-classical workflows and advanced experimental computation through integration with NOUS orchestration and provisioning services.

3.2.1.4 RUNTIME ENVIRONMENT

- **Infrastructure Orchestration.** The Infrastructure Orchestration component automates the provisioning, configuration, and management of infrastructure services required to support computations and workloads executed on the middleware layers (i.e., PaaS, MLaaS). It enables seamless integration and interoperability among heterogeneous infrastructure providers (e.g., multiple cloud providers) and exposes these resources through standardized interfaces.
 - **Configuration.** The Configuration component manages the setup, customization, and lifecycle configuration of infrastructure resources and services. It ensures that all provisioned resources (e.g., VMs, containers, storage volumes, networks) are correctly initialized with the system parameters required by the higher-level services.
 - **Service Provisioning.** The Service Provisioning component automates the creation, allocation, and deployment of infrastructure services. It interacts with Infrastructure Providers to instantiate the necessary computing, storage, and networking resources.
- **Infrastructure Providers.** The Infrastructure Providers represent the core layer of the DSIA, responsible for the physical and virtualized computing, storage, and network resources. These providers offer all the core infrastructure services that support all higher-level components within the DSIP. They include:
 - **Cloud Providers.** Offer elastic, scalable, and on-demand infrastructure resources.
 - **Hypervisors and Operating Systems.** Virtualize and manage physical hardware resources
 - **Virtual Networks and VPNs.** Ensure secure and isolated communication between virtualized environments.
 - **Monitor Agents.** Oversee system health, performance, and usage metrics across distributed infrastructures.
- **Admin Services.** Admin Services provide the operational and management capabilities required to configure and supervise the NIA environment. They ensure that infrastructure resources, platform services, and networking capabilities are configured and monitored in a policy-compliant manner.
 - **Network Orchestrator:** Manages the lifecycle and configuration of virtual networking components across cloud and edge environments, ensuring secure and consistent connectivity.

- **Authorization Service:** Provides policy decision and enforcement capabilities for all infrastructure-level operations within the NOUS ecosystem, ensuring that access requests align with defined governance rules.
- **Encryption / Key Management:** Ensures the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of data and communications across the NOUS infrastructure by managing cryptographic keys, certificates, and encryption mechanisms.
- **Cloud & Edge Computing.** The Cloud and Edge Computing group provides the computational foundation of the NIA, enabling the provisioning, deployment, and management of virtualized and distributed computing environments across cloud and edge domains.
 - **Data Space Provisioning and Management.** Manages the provisioning, configuration, and lifecycle of Data Space-specific environment and services. It enables the creation and maintenance of isolated, compliant, and interoperable execution environment tailored to the needs of Data Space participant.
 - **VM Provisioning.** Provides an abstraction layer for creating and managing virtual machines on the underlying infrastructure. It allows users to use VM instances tailored to their specific computational requirements.
 - **Block storage.** Offers low-level abstraction for provisioning and managing persistent block storage volumes. These volumes allow users to store any form of binary data in fixed-sized blocks, supporting high-performance and transactional workloads.
 - **Container Provisioning.** Enables the deployment, orchestration and monitoring of containerized workloads. It allows users to launch container instances that execute algorithms and applications, offering an alternative to virtual machines when portability is a priority.
 - **Serverless Provisioning.** Provides access to serverless computing capabilities by handling OS-level configuration, system maintenance, and management of underlying compute instances.
 - **File System Provisioning.** Provides an abstraction layer for provisioning various types of file-based storage on the underlying infrastructure, enabling users to utilize these storage resources.
- **Virtual Network and VPN.** The Virtual Network and VPN component establishes secure, isolated, and policy-controlled communication environment across the NOUS ecosystem. It provides virtualized networking capabilities that allow participants and services to communicate over segmented networks, independent of the underlying physical infrastructure. VPN mechanisms are employed to encrypt traffic and create trusted tunnels between distributed nodes, ensuring confidentiality and integrity when data traverses public or hybrid networks.

3.3 DATA SPACE COMMON SERVICES (DATA SHARING)

The Data Space Common Services provide crucial functionalities for the overall management, security, interoperability, and standardization of the NOUS environment. It ensures secure access, identity management, standardized data models, and the discovery and reuse of applications and AI models. These services collectively support the seamless exchange, integration, and analysis of data within the NOUS environment.

3.3.1 SERVICE GATEWAY

The Service Gateway group ensures a unified and secure approach to accessing services and functionalities. It serves as an entry point for the Data Space participants and external actors to interact with the NOUS environment. It provides a standardized API interface and enforcing access

control policies, it enables seamless interaction and collaboration among Data Space participants and external actors. The Service Gateway group includes the following key components:

- **API Gateway.** The API Gateway is a central entry point that provides a unified interface for accessing the functionalities and services available within the Data Space. It manages and exposes APIs that allow Data Space participants to interact with different components and services seamlessly. The API Gateway also handles API request routing, load balancing, and caching to optimize performance and reliability.
- **Policy Enforcement Point (PEP).** The PEP is responsible for enforcing the access control policies defined for the Data Space. It acts as a gatekeeper, evaluating access requests and determining whether they comply with the defined policies and rules. The PEP ensures that only authorized Data Space participants and external actors can access specific resources and functionalities. It enforces policies related to data sharing, data discovery, and other Data Space interactions, enhancing data governance and security.
- **Service Catalogue.** The Service Catalogue is a repository that maintains a comprehensive list of services and functionalities available within the Data Space. It provides a centralized overview of the offerings, making it easier for participants to discover and access the services they require. The Service Catalogue includes detailed information about each service, such as its purpose, API specifications, input/output data formats, and access requirements. It facilitates efficient service discovery and integration within the overall Data Space ecosystem.
- **Network (VPN, Firewall).** The Network component is responsible for establishing secure and isolated communication environments within the NOUS architecture. It enables the creation of private virtual networks (VPNs) to protect data traffic from unauthorized access and external threats. VPNs also facilitate the secure transfer of data and applications both within and across Data Space participants over public networks. In addition, this component supports the configuration of firewall rules to control and restrict inbound and outbound traffic within private networks. By combining network isolation, traffic filtering, and encryption mechanisms, the Network component provides a robust security layer that complements the platform's identity and access management framework, fostering the security within the overall Data Space ecosystem.

3.3.2 IDENTITY AND ACCESS MANAGEMENT

The Identity & Access Management (IAM) group is responsible for managing user identities, providing secure authentication mechanisms, and enforcing fine-grained access control. This way it creates a trusted environment where Data Space participants can confidently collaborate, share data, and engage in circular economy initiatives while protecting sensitive information and maintaining data integrity. The IAM group includes the following key components:

- **Identity Provider Federation.** The Identity Provider is responsible for authenticating and verifying the identities of both users and Data Space participants. It acts as a trusted authority that issues and manages identity credentials – such as usernames and passwords, API tokens, or digital certificates – to ensure secure access to NOUS environment. Through the Identity Provider, Data Space participants can securely onboard to the Data Space ecosystem and assert their identity, and users can obtain access to the platform's services, ensuring that only authorized participants and users are granted access to the system.
- **Authentication Provider Federation.** The Authentication Provider Federation is responsible for establishing trust relationships between different identity providers across multiple domains. It enables users from various organizations or external systems to use their existing identities to access the NOUS environment.
- **Certification Authority.** The Certification Authority is responsible for issuing and managing digital certificates used for secure communication and data exchange within the NOUS environment. Digital certificates serve as cryptographic credentials that verify the authenticity and integrity

of participants' data and communications. By leveraging digital certificates, the Data Space can ensure secure data transmission, data integrity, and non-repudiation, providing a robust foundation for data trustworthiness.

- **Authorization Service.** The Authorization Service, also known as the Policy Decision Point (PDP), is responsible for enforcing access control policies based on the authentication and authorization decisions made by the Identity Provider and other security components. The PDP evaluates access requests against predefined policies to determine whether a user or actor is authorized to perform specific actions or access certain resources within the Data Space.

3.3.3 APPLICATION & DATA DISCOVERY

- **Data & Infrastructure Agent Registry.** The Data and Infrastructure Agent Registry maintains and manages information about all registered Data and Infrastructure Agents within the NOUS ecosystem. It provides a unified directory that enables participants to discover, identify, and interact with available agents across distributed environments.
- **App Catalogue.** The App Catalogue serves as a central repository of applications, tools, and services available within the NOUS ecosystem. It allows participants to discover and access software components relevant to their use cases (e.g., analytic tools, AI frameworks, domain-specific applications, etc.).

3.3.4 DECENTRALIZED LEARNING

The Collective Intelligence component supports federated, and collaborative learning among distributed nodes without requiring centralized data collection. It enables multiple entities to train, refine and evaluate AI models while maintaining data sovereignty and privacy. Local models are trained on participants' private datasets and periodically exchanged to a global entity to be aggregated.

3.4 USER DASHBOARDS & SERVICES

The User Dashboard and Services layer provide the primary interaction interface between end-users and the NOUS ecosystem. It consolidates visualization, configuration, and domain-specific functionalities into intuitive tools that facilitate the exploration, monitoring, and management of the Data Space and applications environment.

- **Domain Specific Applications.** The Domain Specific Applications providers users access to specialized applications and third-party services that complement the NOUS use cases. These applications may include advanced analytics tools, optimization algorithms, or simulation environments tailored to specific domains such as energy, manufacturing, logistics, or sustainability.
- **Data Space Explorer.** The Data Space Explorer acts as a comprehensive interface that allows users to discover and interact with data assets, applications, and services within the NOUS ecosystem. It supports policy and contract management, federated search, metadata exploration, and data asset and resource negotiation and sharing, enabling users to identify relevant resources for analysis, AI model training, and cross-domain collaboration
- **Data Visualizations Dashboards.** The Data Visualization Dashboard enable uses to gain insights through visual representations of data and analytics within the NOUS environment. Using intuitive charts, graphs, and multi-dimensional analysis, users can explore and analyze data. These dashboards promote transparency and decision-making, supporting facilitating the understanding of performance, resource utilization, and environmental impact

- **Configuration/Management Dashboards.** The configuration/management dashboard offers a user-friendly interface for users to configure and manage the Data Space environment and the various services within the NOUS environment. It provides controls for access management, policy settings, system configurations, and monitoring functionalities. Users can customize the Data Space according to their specific requirements, ensuring secure and efficient data exchange, data governance, and overall administration of the Data Space.

3.5 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DSP AND DSIP

The Data Space Participant (DSP) may initiate the provisioning of infrastructure resources based on specific computational, storage, or operational requirements. This interaction establishes a strong coupling between the data management layer, implemented through the NOUS Data Agent (NDA), and the infrastructure provisioning layer, implemented through the NOUS Infrastructure Agent (NIA). Through standardized and interoperable APIs, the NDA can publish, discover, and request dynamic, policy-aware infrastructure and platform services exposed by the DSIP. These services include Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS), and Machine Learning-as-a-Service (MLaaS), all accessible in a unified and federated manner across cloud, edge, and HPC environments.

The DSIP defines the data sharing agreements, governance rules, and usage-control policies established at the DSP level. By evaluating these policies during resource discovery, provisioning, and execution, the DSIP ensures that all infrastructure usage complies with the data sovereignty, security, and federation requirements of the NOUS ecosystem. This guarantees that infrastructure provisioning and workload execution occur in a secure, compliant, and trusted manner across heterogeneous and potentially untrusted actors.

4 NOUS COMPONENT CATALOGUE

4.1 MAPPING OF DOA ELEMENTS TO THE REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

The NOUS reference architecture adopts a multi-layer cloud-to-edge design consisting of several functional components. In this section, each task's objectives and outputs are analyzed and mapped to the corresponding architecture to demonstrate the alignment between the DoA and the NOUS reference architecture (as illustrated in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**).

- “#compute” – HPC & Security: The “compute” layer focuses on designing and implementing the mechanisms required to integrate the HPC and Quantum infrastructures into the NOUS ecosystem. It also includes the development of a cross-cutting cybersecurity framework to enable trust, secure, and policy-compliant execution of workloads across the federated infrastructure environments.
 - Task 3.1 defines the system-level policies, infrastructure requirements, and virtualization strategies necessary to enable seamless interaction between NOUS services and heterogeneous HPC environments. It covers access control, network interfaces, queuing systems, container orchestration, and data repository integration. Key services such as virtualized network and resource management are designed, along with communication protocols to abstract hardware and software heterogeneity across HPC platforms. The task ensures that participants in NOUS can securely and efficiently access HPC capabilities, regardless of the underlying system architecture. (Responsible partner: ARCTUR).
 - Task 3.2 develops a unified software stack to enable hybrid HPC–Quantum workflows. On the Quantum Computing side, it leverages existing frameworks, integrating them with HPC resource managers and runtime systems to allow offloading of compute-intensive tasks. On the HPC side, the task builds mechanisms to invoke quantum instructions from traditional HPC applications using both interpreted (Python-based) and compiled (C/C++) front-ends. A key innovation is the runtime redesign to support multi-user quantum workloads while minimizing idle time. The task also proposes the methodology of the integration of Quantum Machine Learning (QML) with Federated Learning systems, supporting collaborative model training across the compute continuum. (Responsible partner: NCSR).
 - Task 3.3 designs and develops a standalone cybersecurity framework for NOUS, suitable for deployment in both Data Space and cloud-based environments. The approach combines (i) darknets—dedicated, encrypted communication overlays for isolating NOUS services—and (ii) a Zero Trust security model, in which access to services or data is never assumed and is strictly verified via continuous identity, context, and policy evaluation. This architecture supports fine-grained access control, trust minimization, and scalable defense against lateral movement, ensuring all data exchange and workload execution in NOUS are policy-compliant and secure by design (Responsible partner: AEGIS).
- “edge” – Edge Computing and Federated Learning: The “edge” layer focuses on the design and deployment of distributed computing services that span edge, far-edge, and cloud infrastructures. Its goal is to enhance scalability and interoperability by introducing structured parallel programming environments, federated learning frameworks, and dynamic data exchange mechanisms between heterogeneous IoT and edge systems.
 - Task 4.2 delivers a high-performance structured parallel processing environment based on FastFlow, designed for deployment across edge, far-edge, and cloud

systems. The environment supports the instantiation of parallel applications through configurable primitives and user-defined patterns. It includes architectural strategies such as NUMA-aware scheduling, thread pinning, and lock-free communication for meeting low-latency and high-throughput requirements. Integration with the Multi-Transport Communication Library (MTCL) provides protocol-agnostic data transport across a wide range of communication stacks (e.g., TCP/IP, MPI, MQTT, Kafka), ensuring resiliency and fault tolerance. This component is mapped to the Application & Data Orchestration building block and provides the execution underlying technology for distributed NOUS services. (Responsible partner: UNIPi).

- Task 4.3 develops an advanced Federated Learning (FL) framework supporting distributed, privacy-preserving training and inference across resource-constrained devices at the edge and beyond. Built on top of a "analytics-as-a-service" stack, the framework delivers decentralized machine learning algorithms that can adapt to user-centric and device-specific analytics scenarios. A key innovation is the hierarchical orchestration layer, which dynamically allocates training and inference tasks between edge, fog, and cloud tiers, optimizing for energy efficiency, latency, and application-specific constraints. (Responsible partner: ITML).
- Task 4.4 introduces a Plug-and-Interoperate framework for automated and scalable interoperability between heterogeneous IoT and edge systems in the NOUS Data Space. It delivers edge-level interoperability mediators capable of performing data translation and semantic alignment close to the point of data origin. These mediators form a delegated, distributed fog network that supports dynamic configuration and system participation with minimal manual intervention. The component is mapped to the Data Exchange Group within the NOUS Data Agent (NDA) component, serving as an intelligent gateway layer for integrating diverse devices and data standards into the NOUS ecosystem. Integration with semantic tools from T5.4 and configuration logic from T2.4 ensures full alignment with NOUS-wide interoperability specifications. (Responsible partner: UNP).
- "#data" – Data Exchange Services, Applications & Blockchain decentralized data base: The "data" layer focuses on managing, exchanging, and standardizing data assets across a federated and heterogeneous environment. It ensures data sovereignty, transparency, interoperability, and trust through the integration of Data Space protocols, semantic technologies, and Blockchain-based audit and control mechanisms.
 - Task 5.2 delivers a Blockchain-based framework to track data across its entire lifecycle, enabling proof-of-origin, immutability, and compliance monitoring. It supports integration with data sharing and storage operations across cloud and edge systems using low-energy distributed ledger technologies (e.g., Ethereum 2.0, IOTA). Smart contracts and sidechains are used to facilitate interaction with off-ledger data and services. (Responsible partner: POLITO).
 - Task 5.3 builds the core data exchange services of the NOUS ecosystem, enabling connectivity and interoperability between Data Spaces, data pools, and data warehouses. It implements connectors required for enabling the data exchange between existing platforms. These services enable data cataloging, governance, batch/streaming transfers, and cross-space discovery, and form the backbone of the NOUS Data Agent (NDA) component. This includes integration with external platforms (e.g., Crimson, MASA), and the definition of procedures to harmonize shared capabilities across domains. (Responsible partner: INTRA).
 - Task 5.4 delivers the Auto-Standardizer (AS) tool, a key component that automates translation of database schemas into standardized semantic formats. It uses linguistic analysis (e.g., synonyms, language translation) and supervised machine learning to align schema fields, with human-in-the-loop capabilities for refining uncertain matches. The tool integrates with a data lake staging area and supports

multiple data formats and languages. Built using open-source technologies, the Auto-Standardizer facilitates semantic alignment and interoperability for seamless data integration across the NOUS ecosystem. (Responsible partner: AETHON).

- External Platforms:
 - The CRIMSON platform, a European reference system for crisis and emergency management is integrated into NOUS environment to enhance its data lifecycle governance, access control, and traceability for massive, multiformat geospatial and situational data. CRIMSON's use case validates NOUS capabilities in high-stakes, multi-stakeholder environments, including edge-enabled coordination between command centers, mobile responders, and legacy systems (Responsible Partner: CS Group).
 - The MASA (Modena Automotive Smart Area) platform serves as a living lab for testing Cooperative, Connected, and Autonomous Mobility (CCAM). It provides real-time data streams from urban and suburban sensor networks (e.g., video feeds with anonymized object detection), supported by a MEC edge server infrastructure. This use case will demonstrate NOUS integration in mobility scenarios combining edge AI processing, 5G networks, and federated learning environments (Responsible Partner: UNIPI).

FIGURE 5. MAPPING OF DOA ELEMENTS TO THE REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

4.2 DETAILED COMPONENT DESCRIPTION

4.2.1 DATA SPACE CONNECTOR COMPONENT

TABLE 1: DATA SPACE CONNECTOR

General Information											
Component name	Data Space Connector										
Component Description	Core connector enabling policy-governed, sovereign, and secure data exchange between Data Space Participants, using IDS/GAIA-X-aligned protocols. Provides contract negotiation, policy enforcement, asset cataloguing, and data transfer capabilities.										
Architectural Placement	Data Space Participant → NOUS Data Agent → Data Exchange										
Lead Developing Partner	Netcompany										
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management API (configurations, assets, policies, contracts) • DSP endpoint (dsp-url) for inter-participant communication 										
WP/Task	WP5/Task 5.3										
Relevant UC(s)	MS14; potential integration into UC1, UC2, UC3, and UC4										
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	Yes – a front-end for the management API is available, enabling: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring ingoing and outgoing data transfers • Managing contract definitions and agreements • Asset and policy management • Cataloguing and offer discovery • Transfer process instantiation 										
Specifications											
Functional Specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contract negotiation between data providers and consumers • Enforcement of data usage control and sharing policies • Authentication and authorization via identity providers • Secure data exchange over HTTPS and IDS-compliant protocols • Asset publication, catalog browsing, and offer discovery 										
Functional Dependencies	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Function</th> <th>Responsible Component</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Identity verification</td> <td>Identity Provider (e.g., Keycloak)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Persistent storage</td> <td>Object Storage (e.g., Minio, S3)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data transfer via REST APIs</td> <td>Any REST API-compatible service</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Connector-to-connector communication</td> <td>DSP-based data plane communication</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Function	Responsible Component	Identity verification	Identity Provider (e.g., Keycloak)	Persistent storage	Object Storage (e.g., Minio, S3)	Data transfer via REST APIs	Any REST API-compatible service	Connector-to-connector communication	DSP-based data plane communication
	Function	Responsible Component									
	Identity verification	Identity Provider (e.g., Keycloak)									
	Persistent storage	Object Storage (e.g., Minio, S3)									
Data transfer via REST APIs	Any REST API-compatible service										
Connector-to-connector communication	DSP-based data plane communication										

4.2.2 NOUS CYBERSECURITY COMPONENT

TABLE 2: NOUS CYBERSECURITY COMPONENT

General Information	
Component name	NOUS Zero Trust-based Cybersecurity Component
Component Description	Composite component from multiple open-source components for securing the entirety of the NOUS platform with a darknet-like overlay network and Zero Trust workflows
Architectural Placement	Data Space Common Services → Network Data Space Common Services → Policy Enforcement Point Data Space Common Services → Certification Authority Data Space Common Services → Authorization Service

	Data Space Infrastructure Participant → NOUS Infrastructure Agent → Virtual Network & VPN	
Lead Developing Partner	AEIGIS	
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nebula CLI: Used to deploy and manage the Nebula overlay • Keycloak GUI: Used to manage Keycloak • Open Policy Agent CLI: Used to deploy and manage Open Policy Agent policies • Traefik CLI: Used to deploy and manage Traefik access control 	
WP/Task	WP3/Task 3.3	
Relevant UC(s)	UC2	
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	Yes	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	• Installation and management of a darknet-like overlay	
	• Fine-grained traffic flow policies within the Nebula overlay	
	• Encrypted flow of data between Nebula-joined nodes	
	• Fine-grained access control for end-user NOUS services	
	• Hide critical services from public exposure	
	• Continuously monitor sessions and anomalies	
	• Installation and management of a darknet-like overlay	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Secure, Zero Trust-based network connectivity and access control across the NOUS Platform	Underlying infrastructure

4.2.3 AUTO-STANDARDISER COMPONENT

TABLE 3: AUTO-STANDARDISER

General Information		
Component name	Auto-Standardiser (AS)	
Component Description	Automated schema translation tool converting datasets to sector-specific standards using linguistic analysis, ML-based matching, and human-in-the-loop validation.	
Architectural Placement	Data Space Participant → NOUS Data Agent → Application Services → Data Standardization	
Lead Developing Partner	AETHON	
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST API for front-end service that supports human-in-the-loop actions 	
WP/Task	WP5/Task 5.4	
Relevant UC(s)	UC2; other use-cases if standardization is needed	
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	Yes	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	• Automated matching of fields to standards	
	• Human-assisted refinement interface	
	• ML-based matching improvement	
	• Integration with existing data lakes	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Connection to an existing data lake that hosts raw datasets	Data Lake

4.2.4 FEDERATED LEARNING COMPONENT

TABLE 4: FEDERATED LEARNING COMPONENT

General Information		
Component name	Federated Learning Component	
Component Description	Distributed machine learning framework enabling collaborative training and inference.	
Architectural Placement	Data Space Participant → NOUS Data Agent → Application Services → Federated Learning	
Lead Developing Partner	ITML	
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FL Client and FL Server interactions Data Ingestion Interfaces (FL Client side) 	
WP/Task	WP4/Task 4.3	
Relevant UC(s)	UC1, UC2	
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	No	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global model initialization FL Client selection Local model training and aggregation Model registry integration Inference engine 	
	Function	Responsible Component
	Local data ingestion	Local FL Client, Messaging Infrastructure (MQTT, gRPC)
	Local model training	FL Client (executed on edge/cloud node)
	Model update transfer	FL Client → FL Server (via HTTP, gRPC)
Model Aggregation	FL Server Aggregator Module	

4.2.5 PARALLEL PROCESSING COMPONENT

TABLE 5: PARALLEL PROCESSING COMPONENT

General Information		
Component name	Parallel Processing Component (Python-FastFlow)	
Component Description	Python bindings enabling parallel data-parallel pipelines without GIL limitations using FastFlow patterns.	
Architectural Placement	Data Space Participant → NOUS Data Agent → Application Services → Parallel Processing	
Lead Developing Partner	UNIFI	
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disk I/O Kafka pub/sub 	
WP/Task	WP4/Task 4.2	
Relevant UC(s)	UC1 for image processing;	
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	No	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build distributed parallel DAGs Pipelines/Farms patterns Kafka or disk ingestion Stateless parallel execution 	
	Function	Responsible Component
	Disk I/O	Any storage
	Pub/Sub	Kafka Broker

4.2.6 ORACLE COMPONENT

TABLE 6: ORACLE COMPONENT

General Information																			
Component name	Oracle System																		
Component Description	Microservices-based blockchain platform enabling reliable, auditable, and real-time data flow between external sources (REST APIs, MQTT, WebSockets) and blockchain networks. Supports multiple oracle modes, consensus, telemetry, and node automation.																		
Architectural Placement	Data Space Infrastructure Participant → NOUS Infrastructure Agent → PaaS → Blockchain																		
Lead Partner Developing	AIR Institute																		
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST/HTTP JSON for front-end, integrators, and external services • MQTT 3.1.1/5.0 for IoT ingestion • WebSocket protocol for real-time task-trigger messaging • JSON-RPC towards blockchain node • gRPC for internal communication between microservices 																		
WP/Task	WP5/Task 5.2																		
Relevant UC(s)	UC1, UC3																		
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	Yes – configuration UI and live status dashboards																		
Specifications																			
Functional Specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage oracle definitions and ACL • Generate node deployment packages • Collect logs, telemetry, metrics • Execute modular ingestion, processing, actuation pipelines • Consensus-based value finalization • SLA alerts and monitoring • Full traceability for audit 																		
Functional Dependencies																			
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Function</th> <th>Responsible Component</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Configuration & ACL</td> <td>Oracle Configuration Service</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Node package generation</td> <td>Oracle Generation Service</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Telemetry storage</td> <td>Oracle Monitoring Service and MongoDB/Redis</td> </tr> <tr> <td>External data ingestion</td> <td>Data-fetch and MQTT modules</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Trigger evaluation</td> <td>Task-trigger module</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data processing</td> <td>Data-processing module</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Action execution</td> <td>Actuator module</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Consensus & finalization</td> <td>Smart contract suit on target blockchain</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Function	Responsible Component	Configuration & ACL	Oracle Configuration Service	Node package generation	Oracle Generation Service	Telemetry storage	Oracle Monitoring Service and MongoDB/Redis	External data ingestion	Data-fetch and MQTT modules	Trigger evaluation	Task-trigger module	Data processing	Data-processing module	Action execution	Actuator module	Consensus & finalization	Smart contract suit on target blockchain
Function	Responsible Component																		
Configuration & ACL	Oracle Configuration Service																		
Node package generation	Oracle Generation Service																		
Telemetry storage	Oracle Monitoring Service and MongoDB/Redis																		
External data ingestion	Data-fetch and MQTT modules																		
Trigger evaluation	Task-trigger module																		
Data processing	Data-processing module																		
Action execution	Actuator module																		
Consensus & finalization	Smart contract suit on target blockchain																		

4.2.7 BLOCKCHAIN COMPONENT

TABLE 7: BLOCKCHAIN COMPONENT

General Information	
Component name	Blockchain Component
Component Description	European Blockchain (EBSI) compatible BESU-based distributed ledger storing transactions, smart contract outputs, and references to off-chain data (IPFS, metadata).
Architectural Placement	Data Space Infrastructure Participant → NOUS Infrastructure Agent → PaaS → Blockchain

Lead Developing Partner	POLITO	
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enables interactions with the core components for transaction submission, smart contract invocation, event retrieval and transaction confirmation. 	
WP/Task	WP5/Task 5.2	
Relevant UC(s)	All with on-chain requirements	
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	No	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Verify and accept transactions Execute contract logic Emit immutable event logs Store references to off-chain data 	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Off-chain data input	External Oracles

4.2.8 EVM BRIDGE COMPONENT

TABLE 8: EVM BRIDGE COMPONENT

General Information		
Component name	EVM Bridge	
Component Description	TypeScript-based framework enabling type-safe contract interaction, event synchronization, wallet management, and automated wrapper generation for Ethereum-compatible blockchains.	
Architectural Placement	Data Space Infrastructure Participant → NOUS Infrastructure Agent → PaaS → Blockchain	
Lead Developing Partner	AIR Institute / University of Salamanca	
Interfaces Description	Generator API:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Command Line Interface: generate-contract-wrapper transforms compiled contract artifacts Produces TypeScript wrappers with methods interfaces matching contract ABIs. 	
	Service API:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BlockchainService: for wallet management, transaction configuration, and block synchronization Blockchain event scanner: for monitoring contract events with configurable polling intervals Wallet Provider: for secure wallet access password-protected key management 	
WP/Task	WP5/Task 5.3	
Relevant UC(s)	UC1, UC1	
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	No	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contract Wrapper Generation Wallet Management Blockchain interaction Event Processing Smart contract deployment 	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Smart contract invocation	EVM Bridge
	Transaction submission	EVM Bridge
	Event scanning and synchronization	EVM Bridge
	Wallet management and transaction signing	EVM Bridge
	JSON-RPC and WebSocket communication	Ethereum Node (e.g., Geth, Besu)

TypeScript wrapper generation	Generator API (@asanrom/smart-contract-wrapper)
Block and event state persistence	Application Database
Contract artifact generation	Truffle (deprecated) moving to HardHat. Solidity Compiler
Real-time blockchain event propagation	WebSocket interface + App Backend
Transaction result processing	App Backend (integrated via Bridge APIs)
Smart contract Deployer	Truffle (deprecated) moving to HardHat

4.2.9 PLUG'N'PLAY INTEROPERABILITY MIDDLEWARE

TABLE 9: PLUG'N'PLAY INTEROPERABILITY MIDDLEWARE

General Information									
Component name	Plug'n'Play Interoperability Middleware								
Component Description	Middleware translating heterogeneous data models between sources and consumers using specifications stored in an Interoperability Catalogue.								
Architectural Placement	Data Space Participant → NOUS Data Agent → Application Services → Edge Interoperability Mediator								
Lead Developing Partner	UNP								
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REST APIs for managing interoperability specifications, data sources, and data consumers MQTT/REST for data transfer between data source to data consumer 								
WP/Task	WP4 / Task 4.4								
Relevant UC(s)	UC1								
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	Yes								
Specifications									
Functional Specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Store interoperability specifications Execute transformations Semantic proxy for source/consumer registration Best-path algorithm 								
Functional Dependencies	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Function</th> <th>Responsible Component</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Data subscription/request</td> <td>Application on Edge Node (via PARALLEL PROCESSING COMPONENT)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Register data source (Data source descriptor and data format used)</td> <td>Data Source provider</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Translate data (between different data models)</td> <td>PLUG'N'PLAY Mediator</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Function	Responsible Component	Data subscription/request	Application on Edge Node (via PARALLEL PROCESSING COMPONENT)	Register data source (Data source descriptor and data format used)	Data Source provider	Translate data (between different data models)	PLUG'N'PLAY Mediator
	Function	Responsible Component							
	Data subscription/request	Application on Edge Node (via PARALLEL PROCESSING COMPONENT)							
Register data source (Data source descriptor and data format used)	Data Source provider								
Translate data (between different data models)	PLUG'N'PLAY Mediator								

4.2.10 SCIENTIFIC HPC ANALYTICS

TABLE 10: SCIENTIFIC HPC ANALYTICS

General Information	
Component name	Scientific Data HPC Storage and AI Analytics
Component Description	HPC-based ML modeling and LLM-powered CLI assistant to support researchers which scientific dataset and job management.
Architectural Placement	Data Space Infrastructure Participant → NOUS Infrastructure Agent → MLaaS → AI Provisioning (IaaS → HPC)
Lead Developing Partner	NCSR

Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLI-based interface 	
WP/Task	WP7 / Task 7.2	
Relevant UC(s)	UC4	
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	No	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train ML models on HPC nodes • Evaluate and stores results • LLM chatbot assisting user queries • Best execution 	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Natural Language Query Processing	Chatbot (LLM-based)
	User Interaction Handling via CLI	Chatbot interface
	ML model training on HPC	Predictive model

4.2.11 CRIMSON PLATFORM

TABLE 11: CRIMSON EXTERNAL PLATFORM

General Information		
Component name	Crimson	
Component Description	European reference platform for crisis management. It enables the sharing of geospatial and situational information on a need-to-know basis between multiple stakeholders in several interconnected command centres and first responders on the field.	
Architectural Placement	Data Space Participant → NOUS Data Agent → Applications & Data Orchestration → External Apps & Services	
Lead Developing Partner	CS Group	
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rest API 	
WP/Task	WP7/Task 7.2	
Relevant UC(s)	UC3	
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	Yes, to access and update information related to crisis.	
Specifications		
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Interoperability through Data Space	Data Space components
	Traceability of data	Blockchain components

4.2.12 MASA PLATFORM

TABLE 12: MASA EXTERNAL PLATFORM

General Information	
Component name	MASA
Component Description	MASA is conceived as a unified urban digital platform that provides a coherent, privacy-preserving layer for sensing, processing, and exploiting mobility-related data at city scale. From the point of view of users and applications, MASA acts as a single logical system that ingests heterogeneous urban signals (e.g., smart cameras, roadside sensors, vehicles, and IoT devices), transforms them into standardized and anonymized mobility metadata, and makes this information available in real time to multiple services. The platform abstracts away device-specific details and deployment complexity, exposing a consistent data plane and interaction model that applications can rely on regardless of where data is

	generated or consumed. MASA supports low-latency, edge-aware operation by seamlessly spanning sensing areas and MEC environments, allowing analytics and decision-making to occur close to data sources while remaining fully integrated with city-level services. By enforcing privacy-by-design principles and role-based data access, MASA enables the safe reuse of mobility data across domains such as traffic monitoring, vulnerable road user safety, urban planning, and situational awareness. Overall, MASA functions as a single, integrated platform that turns raw urban observations into actionable, interoperable knowledge for smart-city applications, rather than as a collection of isolated services.										
Architectural Placement	Data Space Participant → NOUS Data Agent → Applications & Data Orchestration → External Apps & Services										
Lead Developing Partner	UNIMORE										
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MQTT pub/sub • Rest API 										
WP/Task	WP7/Task 7.2										
Relevant UC(s)	UC1										
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	No										
Specifications											
Functional Specifications	Support communication with NOUS Data Space										
Functional Dependencies	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Function</th> <th>Responsible Component</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Extract geo-located metadata from video streams</td> <td>Video processing node</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Forecast collisions among road users</td> <td>VRU component</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sent user's location update and receive collision alerting messages</td> <td>MASA-NOUS application</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Export data in NOUS Data Space</td> <td>MASA-NOUS Bridge</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Function	Responsible Component	Extract geo-located metadata from video streams	Video processing node	Forecast collisions among road users	VRU component	Sent user's location update and receive collision alerting messages	MASA-NOUS application	Export data in NOUS Data Space	MASA-NOUS Bridge
	Function	Responsible Component									
	Extract geo-located metadata from video streams	Video processing node									
	Forecast collisions among road users	VRU component									
Sent user's location update and receive collision alerting messages	MASA-NOUS application										
Export data in NOUS Data Space	MASA-NOUS Bridge										

4.2.13 CHATBOT

TABLE 13: CHATBOT

General Information	
Component name	Chatbot
Component Description	The Chatbot is the application-level component that acts as the central orchestrator of the RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation) system. Its primary function is to provide a Conversational User Interface (CUI) integrated into the HPC and VirtualLab portals. Unlike a simple chat bot, this component coordinates the business logic required to transform a user query into an answer grounded in technical data, managing user identity, historical context, and semantic information retrieval.
Architectural Placement	User Dashboards and Services → Domain Specific Applications
Lead Developing Partner	USAL
Interfaces Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chat Interface (Conversation API): Exposes an endpoint (REST/WebSocket) for the frontend widgets embedded in HPC/VirtualLab portals. It handles user messages, history retrieval, and delivers the final generated answers. • Ingestion Interface (Data Connector): A backend interface that actively monitors and ingests data from connected sources (HPC and VirtualLab databases). It handles text extraction, chunking, and vectorization automatically.
WP/Task	T6.4
Relevant UC(s)	UC4
Interfaces with End-users (yes/no)	A front-end application (Chat Widget) is provided to end-users in the portals, offering:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural language querying (Text/Voice). • Contextualized technical answers with source citations. • Access to conversation history. 	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	End-to-End RAG Orchestration: Manages the flow: User Query -> Vector Search -> Context Retrieval -> LLM Generation -> Answer.	
	Semantic Search: Performs high-dimensional similarity searches (ANN) on the indexed data.	
	Session Management: Maintains stateful conversation history per user.	
	Security & Filtering: Ensures users only retrieve data they are authorized to access.	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	User Identification	Identity & Access Management
	Raw Data Access	HPC Systems & VirtualLab (Data Sources)
	Compute Resources	HPC Infrastructure
	History and Vector Storage	History Database (PaaS)

5 INSTANTIATION OF THE REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

This section presents three instantiation examples of the NOUS Reference Architecture, illustrating how the architectural building blocks can be applied to implement concrete workflows and interactions for different scenarios.

5.1 DATA SPACE – EXTERNAL APPLICATIONS INSTANTIATION EXAMPLE

Figure 6 presents an instantiation example of the reference architecture (as introduced in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**), with a focus on enabling event-driven data exchange and synchronization between distributed applications or platforms. This example highlights how external services acting as Data Providers and/or Data Consumers interact with core Data Space components to publish, discover, and securely exchange event-based data assets.

FIGURE 6. DATA SPACE - EXTERNAL APPLICATIONS EXAMPLE

5.1.1 DATA PROVIDER

On the provider side, an Event Platform emits new event data into the Data Bus, which implements a topic-based publish/subscribe mechanism. The Raw Event Sync component handles these events and triggers the synchronization operations required for updating the Event Repository in the Persistence layer, ensuring long-term storage of the event-based data. The Event/DS Explorer UI is a key component in the architecture that bridges the gap between the event data management and Data Space operations. It provides a user-friendly web interface that allows users to explore, configure, and manage the event-based data and their data sharing configurations. The Explorer acts as the main point of interaction with the Event Sync component, offering visibility into which

data events are available, how they are structured and how they are exposed to the EDC Data Exchange component. The main function of the Event/DS Explorer UI is to enable filtering before event-based data assets are published to the Data Space. Users can select which subset of the events should be included in the shared data plane, ensuring only relevant and approved information is made accessible to external parties. The Event Sync module registers the event-based data assets within the EDC Control Plane, where the corresponding metadata are published and made discoverable to Data Space participants. The EDC Data Plane then supports the secure and policy-compliant data transfer, delivering the filtered event-based data to authorized consumers.

5.1.2 DATA CONSUMER

On the consumer side, a similar mechanism ensures seamless synchronization and consuming of event-based data assets. Through the Event/DS Explorer UI, consumers can discover available offerings, initiate data transfer workflows, and leverage the Event Sync component to receive and store event-based data assets to the Persistence layer based on specific configurations. The EDC Control Plane facilitates the discovery and negotiation of event-based data assets, while the EDC Data Plane executes the secure and policy-compliant transfer of data in accordance with the negotiated contracts and sharing policies established during the data exchange process.

5.1.3 DATA SPACE COMMON SERVICES (DATA SHARING)

The interactions between Data Space participants are governed and secured through the Data Space Common Services vertical layer, which provides functionalities for the overall management, security, and interoperability of the Data Space. This layer incorporates the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) that ensures only authorized and authenticated users can access the platform's services. The Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service, supported by an OAuth2 Authorization Server and a Certification Authority ensure that all data transactions comply with established identity, authentication, and trust policies among Data Space participants. Furthermore, the EDC Data Registry, as part of the Data Digital Models and Vocabularies, maintains standardized metadata, digital asset descriptions, and interoperability vocabularies, thereby ensuring semantic consistency and discoverability of the exchanged information across the Data Space environment.

5.2 DATA SPACE – FEDERATED LEARNING INSTANTIATION EXAMPLE

Figure 7 presents an instantiation example of the reference architecture (as introduced in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**), which focus on enabling model exchange and synchronization required for the federated learning workflows. This example extends the main architecture by focusing on how distributed entities—each operating as an Edge FL Runtime – leverage the Data Space components to publish, discover, and synchronize ML models.

FIGURE 7. DATA SPACE - FEDERATED LEARNING INSTANTIATION EXAMPLE

5.2.1 LOCAL FL AGENTS

Local data sources—such as physical elements, IoT systems, or industrial processes—generate continuous data streams that are ingested through the Data Bus using a topic-based publish/subscribe mechanism. Incoming events from the Data Bus are first processed by the Data Processing component, which transforms heterogeneous raw inputs into standardized and structured representations required for federated learning and execution. More specifically, Data Processing performs schema translation using techniques such as linguistic analysis, supervised machine learning for schema-field alignment, and optional human-in-the-loop refinement for ambiguous mappings. Integrated with a local staging area or data lake, the Data Processing module ensures that all downstream components receive harmonized data regardless of the original format, language, or schema. Once data has been standardized, the Raw Event Sync component triggers synchronization workflows with the Local FL Agent. This includes preparing model-ready datasets and orchestrating the execution of local training. The Local FL Agent performs model training and manages the lifecycle of model artifacts stored in the Local Model Repository. The FL/DS Dashboard UI provides a unified interface for monitoring training progress and configuring model-sharing

policies. It interacts with the FL Agent Sync component, which validates and publishes local model updates to the Data Space via the EDC Data Exchange. This ensures that only policy-compliant and authorized models are made available within the Data Space and become discoverable for the global aggregation process.

5.2.2 GLOBAL FL AGENT

The Global FL Agent coordinates federated model aggregation across all participants in the Data Space. It consumes local model updates shared via the EDC Data Exchange—using the Control Plane for negotiation and policy enforcement and the Data Plane for secure transfer. Upon receiving local models, the Global FL Agent stores them in the Global Model Repository and executes standardized aggregation techniques (e.g., FedAvg or domain-specific variants). This produces a consolidated global model that reflects learning across all participants while preserving strict data sovereignty. Once aggregation is complete, the global model is published back into the Data Space as a discoverable asset. Local FL Agents can then retrieve it for: initializing the next round of local training, or direct inference within the participant's operational environment. This iterative loop enables continuous improvement and system-wide adaptation without exchanging raw data.

5.2.3 DATA SPACE COMMON SERVICES.

The interactions between Local FL Agents and the Global FL Agent are governed and secured through the Data Space Common Services vertical layer, which provides the functionality required for overall management, security, and interoperability within the Data Space. The Reverse Proxy and Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) authenticate incoming requests and enforces usage-control policies, ensuring that all exchanges comply with established trust and governance rules. The Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service, including OAuth2 Authorization Servers and the Certification Authority issues verifiable identities and enforces access control tailored to each participant. To support the discovery and execution of applications within the Data Space, the Application Discovery Services integrate the App Catalogue, which serves as the registry for learning applications and enables participants to discover, evaluate, and adopt applications relevant to their federated learning workflows. The Artifact Repository complements this by storing the software artifacts—such as learning components, libraries, and dependencies—required for deploying and executing those applications. Applications listed in the App Catalogue reference the artifacts stored in the repository, ensuring that participants can reliably deploy and run them. Together, these services establish a trusted environment in which model updates, global aggregation workflows, and application-level integrations occur seamlessly and securely across all Data Space Participants.

5.3 DATA SPACE – INFRASTRUCTURE PROVISIONING INSTANTIATION EXAMPLE

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. presents an instantiation example of the reference architecture (as introduced in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**) that enables infrastructure consumers to discover and access the computational resources required to execute their workloads in a secure and efficient manner. This example extends the main architecture by focusing on the interactions between an infrastructure provider and an infrastructure consumer, highlighting how infrastructure resources are published, discovered, and used through the Data Space environment, while their actual usage relies on native infrastructure access mechanisms.

FIGURE 8. DATA SPACE - INFRASTRUCTURE PROVISIONING INSTANTIATION EXAMPLE

5.3.1 INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER

The Infrastructure Provider acts as a key enabler of federated infrastructure provisioning within the Data Space. It exposes available computational resources, such as IaaS, MLaaS, and HPC-related offerings by publishing resource metadata descriptors that make these resources discoverable and available within the NOUS environment. The Resource Publisher component is responsible for publishing these offerings using standardized metadata descriptions that describe resource capabilities, constraints, availability, and usage policies. These metadata descriptors enable infrastructure resources to be discoverable and negotiable without exposing the actual resources. The Resource/DS Dashboard UI provides a unified interface for monitoring, managing, and configuring published infrastructure assets. Through this interface, the Infrastructure Provider can define resource visibility, sharing conditions, and policy constraints, ensuring that infrastructure offerings are exposed in a controlled and policy-compliant manner across the federated environment.

5.3.2 INFRASTRUCTURE CONSUMER

The Infrastructure Consumer discovers available infrastructure resources by querying the metadata descriptors published in the Data Space. Discovery and negotiation are performed through Data Space mechanisms, including the EDC Control Plane, which supports negotiation and agreement establishment. Once the relevant resource descriptors and access policies are evaluated, the Infrastructure Consumer does not consume the infrastructure via Data Space protocols. Instead, it accesses and uses the selected computational resources through the native interfaces and protocols provided by the Infrastructure Provider (e.g., cloud APIs, HPC schedulers, Kubernetes

APIs, or vendor-specific management interfaces), as specified in the resource metadata. This approach ensures compatibility with existing infrastructure ecosystems, avoids unnecessary protocol overhead, and enables seamless execution of workloads while remaining compliant with the governance rules negotiated through the Data Space.

5.3.3 COMMON DATA SPACE SERVICES

The Data Space Common Services horizontal layer ensures that all interactions among infrastructure providers and consumers are secure, policy-compliant, and interoperable. It provides the foundational mechanisms for identity management, trust establishment, access control, and governance across the ecosystem. This layer integrates the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) and Reverse Proxy, which regulate access to Data Space services and ensure that only authorized and authenticated participants can publish or discover resource metadata. The Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS), in conjunction with an OAuth2 Authorization Server and a Certification Authority, supports authentication and authorization, ensuring compliance with trust and policy requirements. In addition, the EDC Data Registry as part of the Data Digital Models and Vocabularies layer, maintains standardized metadata descriptors, digital asset representations, and interoperability vocabularies. This guarantees semantic consistency, discoverability, and alignment of infrastructure resource descriptions across the federated Data Space. The Service Catalogue complements these capabilities by providing a unified view of available infrastructure and data services, enabling efficient discovery and integration by infrastructure consumers.

6 OPEN-SOURCE DEVELOPMENT PLATFORM AND BEST PRACTICES

Eclipse Research Labs provides a suite of infrastructure (GitLab), analytical tools, and training to foster the implementation of open-source best practices from the outset, enhancing the likelihood of producing high-quality, professional open-source outcomes. For NOUS, this translates into a set of principles.

6.1 KEY PRINCIPLES

Open Collaboration. NOUS leverages an open infrastructure (namely Eclipse Research Labs GitLab³) to enable consortium members to collaborate transparently from the project's early stages, adhering to the principle of early and frequent integration. This framework incorporates automated Continuous Integration (CI) processes to validate contributions, ensuring that functional regressions and integration errors are detected and resolved early in the lifecycle. It also helps in clearly identifying which parts of the project will be open source, which are undecided, and which will remain proprietary, thus preventing last-minute surprises regarding exploitation plans.

Transparency. The platform promotes an open work environment where the development process is visible to all, reducing the risk of work being lost in obscurity among countless public repositories. By clearly articulating development plans and decisions, it ensures that early project results are readily communicated to external stakeholders, enhancing transparency.

Community Governance. Through a Contributor Agreement, contributors to NOUS's open-source repositories are identified and listed from the outset. Contributors must sign the Eclipse Contributor Agreement (ECA)⁴ to contribute code, ensuring proper governance and recognition.

Open-Source Licenses. The choice of open-source licenses for NOUS's outputs is strategic, aiming for business-friendly licenses. To this end, the project has established a framework prioritizing permissive and weak copyleft licenses, specifically the Apache 2.0 License, MIT License, or Eclipse Public License 2.0. This selection promotes broad adoption and minimal friction for commercial exploitation and integration with the components described in the NOUS Component Catalogue.

IP Reviews and Best Practices. Regular Intellectual Property (IP) Reviews are conducted alongside checks for open-source Best Practices (BP) to analyze the code early in the development process. This dual-focus approach ensures legal compliance by verifying copyright headers and managing third-party dependency license compatibility, while simultaneously enforcing high project standards through the inclusion of essential documentation (such as README, LICENSE, and CONTRIBUTING files). The commitment to transparency and compliance is further supported by the public documentation of operational guidance and best practices on the NOUS Research Labs GitLab wiki⁵.

Training and Education. To further embed open-source best practices and ensure all contributors are well-informed, two dedicated webinars were conducted for the NOUS consortium. The "Open Collaboration and Open Development" webinar, held on September 11, 2024, provided a foundational overview of Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS). The "Open-Source Licenses and Best Practices" webinar, held on March 11, 2025, provided an in-depth look at the strategic selection of business-friendly licenses and the procedures for continuous IP review and compliance with Best Practices (BP). These training initiatives have been crucial in fostering a culture of high-quality, professional open-source contribution from the NOUS consortium members.

6.2 NOUS RESEARCH LABS

The NOUS Research Labs were provisioned in M6, with hosting provided by the Eclipse Foundation at OVH in France. This location is particularly significant for a European-focused project, as it ensures compliance with European privacy and data protection laws, reinforcing the commitment to

a sovereign, open European data ecosystem. By the time of this report (M24), the project has seen significant growth in engagement. The number of contributors who have signed the Eclipse Contributor Agreement and joined the NOUS team on GitLab is currently 27. It now comprises a total of 16 repositories, which closely match the NOUS components detailed in Section 4 (e.g., Data Space Connector, Zero Trust Component) and are actively used to track the entire development process, from planning to coding.

Analytical data from the past three months also shows that the repositories have had 79 commits by 9 unique contributors. This active engagement demonstrates that the project partners are developing in the open, adhering to best practices for collaboration and transparency.

Regarding the project's governance, the process for IP review and compliance with open-source best practices is progressing according to plan. An exhaustive review was completed by M24, which yielded the following results:

- 1924 third-party dependencies were scanned and verified. No issues were found.
- 7 issues related to best practices opened and subsequently closed.

This process is continuous, involving the ongoing addition of copyright headers and the revision of best practices.

TABLE 14: NOUS RESEARCH LABS IP AND BP STATUS BY M24

Group	Repository	Visibility	LICENSE	IP Status	README
-	nous-docs	public	Eclipse Public License 2.0	OK	README.md OK
common-administration-services	decentralised-services/blockchain_for_cloud_and_edge_storage	public	MIT License	OK	README.md OK
common-administration-services	decentralised-services/edge-cloud-mqtt-layer	public	MIT License	OK	README.md OK
common-administration-services	decentralised-services/evm-bridge	public	MIT License	OK	README.md OK
common-administration-services	iaas-services/hpc-qc-interface	public	MIT License	OK	readme.md OK
common-administration-services	security-services/nous-cybersecurity-component	public	MIT License	OK	README.md OK
common-administration-services	security-services/nous-iam-component	public	Apache License 2.0	OK	README.md OK
data-spaces-participants	adapters/nous-data-exchange-agent	public	Eclipse Public License 2.0	OK	README.md OK
data-spaces-participants	application-services/fastflow-python	public	MIT License	OK	README.md OK
data-spaces-participants	application-services/federated-learning/fl-component	public	Apache License 2.0	OK	README.md OK
data-spaces-participants	data-agent/nous-dataspace-connector	public	Apache License 2.0	OK	README.md OK
use-cases	use_case_2	public	MIT License	OK	Readme.md OK
use-cases	use_case_4_bayesian_optimization_for_design_space_exploration	public	Apache License 2.0	OK	README.md OK
use-cases	use_case_4_density_aware_greedy_sampling	public	Apache License 2.0	OK	README.md OK
use-cases	use-case-1	public	MIT License	OK	README.md OK

Table 14 provides a summary of the latest status per project, indicating a strong adoption of best open-source practices and adequate compliance regarding IP.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presented the NOUS Reference Architecture and Open-Source Development Platform, providing a comprehensive and structured view of the architectural foundations that enable secure, federated, and policy-aware data and infrastructure collaboration across heterogeneous environments. The document consolidates the architectural concepts, design decisions, and building blocks developed within the project, offering a unified reference for the NOUS ecosystem.

The core contribution of this deliverable is the definition of a layered and modular reference architecture, structured around the Data Space Participant (DSP), the Data Space Infrastructure Participant (DSIP), and the Data Space Common Services. Within this architecture, the NOUS Data Agent (NDA) and the NOUS Infrastructure Agent (NIA) play central roles in enabling data exchange, application orchestration, infrastructure discovery, and resource provisioning, while ensuring compliance with data sovereignty, security, and governance requirements. The architecture explicitly decouples resource discovery and governance from execution and consumption, allowing infrastructure and services to be accessed through native protocols while remaining discoverable and governed through the Data Space.

In addition to the architectural definition, this deliverable has described the open-source development platform that supports the instantiation, integration, and deployment of NOUS components. By leveraging open standards, interoperable interfaces, and widely adopted technologies, the NOUS platform promotes extensibility, reusability, and alignment with European Data Space initiatives. The document has further illustrated the applicability of the NOUS Reference Architecture through a set of representative instantiation examples, demonstrating how the architectural building blocks can be combined to support concrete workflows involving data sharing, infrastructure provisioning, and distributed execution across cloud, edge, and high-performance computing environments. These examples serve as reference patterns that guide future deployments and validate the architectural design choices made within the project.

Overall, this deliverable establishes a solid technical foundation for the NOUS project. In subsequent project phases, the reference architecture and development platform will be further refined, implemented, and validated through pilot use cases and experimental deployments. Feedback from these activities will inform future iterations of the architecture, ensuring its robustness, scalability, and relevance for real-world Data Space and federated infrastructure scenarios.